

Speculation on Energy and Potential Energy and Their Direct Link to Force

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 9, 2026

In Newtonian mechanics, force and energy are clearly separated. For example, $pp/2m = \int F dx = \int dp/dt dx = m/2 v^2 = pp/2m$. The equation $pp/2m + V(x) = E$ is considered to be strictly an energy equation. In special relativity, $m_0 c^2$ is considered to be strictly an energy.

We have suggested in previous notes that m_0 is proportional to inertia which is a force. Thus, m_0 and $m_0 c^2$ are thought of in two very different manners simultaneously, i.e. as an energy and as a force. We propose that it might be beneficial to think of both m_0 and $V(x)$ in terms of energy and force distribution simultaneously. In particular, we consider that $V(x)$ is not only potential energy at x , but is also linked to force or interaction at x through $-d/dx V(x)$. The reason this duality of energy-force may be important is that it is directly linked to quantum mechanics, we argue.

In general, it is argued that classical mechanics is a high energy level limit of quantum mechanics. We argue, however, that for a single particle bound state, the energy linked with a momentum p (at any energy level) is $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic) which is deterministic (and also follows from special relativity) and has nothing to do with quantum mechanics. The difference between classical mechanics and quantum, is that there exists an interaction (impulse hit) probability of $\exp(ipx)$ which means that instead of a hit occurring at the center-of-mass point, it may occur within an \hbar/p range. Thus, one may have a particle interact and move through either of two slits if they are separated by about \hbar/p . If p , however, is changed in an interaction, $p_1 \rightarrow p_2$, then the change in energy $p_2^2/2m - p_1^2/2m$ (one dimension) is classical-deterministic. It is, however, the duality of $V(x)$ with force that force one to consider not only energy $pp/2m$ (deterministic), but also its associated force distribution given by $\exp(ipx) / W(x)$, where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

As a result, one creates the average kinetic energy term: $\{ \sum_p a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x)$. One may call $\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ a probability and so formally one has $KE_{ave}(x)$, but physically $\exp(ipx)$ represents a force distribution. The balance to $V(x)$ is a combination of a deterministic energy $pp/2m$ with a force distribution $\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. This, we argue, is a physical statement and helps to describe why $V(x)$ may be expanded as a series of virtual particles (e.g. photons etc). It is not just energy, but force that must be considered together. It is only in classical physics, $pp/2m + V(x) = E$ that one solely considers the energy aspects, i.e. $pp/2m$ and $V(x)$ only as energy, but the more general picture, we argue, is to consider not only energy, but force distribution together. This is the quantum picture and it incorporates not only probability, but deterministic Newtonian mechanics (or special relativity) through the use of $pp/2m$.

The Notion of Energy Linked with Momentum in Quantum Mechanics

The notion of kinetic energy ($pp/2m$), for a momentum p first appeared in Newtonian mechanics through:

$$dp/dt = F \text{ (Newton's second law)} \quad ((1a)) \quad \int dp dx/dt = \int F dx = pp/2m \quad ((1b))$$

It also, however, arises in special relativity by taking the $v \ll c$ limit of

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} = m_0 c^2 + p^2/2m + \dots \quad ((2))$$

Quantum mechanics is considered to represent a very new kind of physics and it is sometimes said that it becomes classical physics in the high energy limit. This is formally called the Correspondence Principle. We have argued previously and argue again that classical physics is embedded into quantum. In particular,

((3a)) The use of $p^2/2m$ in calculating $K_{E_{ave}}(x)$ for any energy level in a quantum bound state problem (nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation) means that both classical Newtonian and special relativity are respected at least as part of the picture. One may say that the change of p to p^2 follows at least mathematically in the same manner as special relativity or Newtonian mechanics. Otherwise, one could not use $p^2/2m$.

((3b)) $x=vt$ should hold for the center-of-mass of a quantum particle as special relativity is based on this equation and $E=m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ follows from special relativity and yields $p^2/2m + m_0 c^2$ in the $v \ll c$ limit. Thus, one cannot use $p^2/2m$ without also acknowledging $x=vt$ for the center-of-mass we argue.

It seems that much deterministic classical physics is present in quantum mechanics. The key difference is that a free particle does not render its impulse hit or E change at the center-of-mass. In space, it renders its impulse hit in a probabilistic manner governed by:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

The next question becomes: What physical implications does this have?

For an interaction with a 2-slit apparatus with slit separation about \hbar/p , $\exp(ipx)$ suggests that the particle may probabilistically interact with both slits. One may point out, however, that if it interacts with slit 1, it travels in a straight line from slit 1 to a point on a screen and the same statement holds for slit 2. This is a manifestation of $x=vt$. The catch is that one must add probabilities in an OR situation.

$$\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2) \quad \text{where } r_1 \text{ is a vector from slit 1 to a point on a screen and } r_2, \text{ from slit 2 to the same point} \quad ((5))$$

In a bound state problem, one might ask: What is the relevance of ((4))? A potential $V(x)$ in Newtonian mechanics represents energy at x . It also represents force through $-d/dx V(x)$ and it is this force which changes $\exp(ipx)$. In such a case, the force picture must also be respected and this involves $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that like m_0 being inertia as well as energy, one must think of $V(x)$ as not only being energy as in the Newtonian case, but also of being directly linked to the force in x profile. As a result, average kinetic energy should really be $p^2/2m$ (

deterministic value) multiplied by the force profile as well. We argue that this is new physics (quantum physics) and leads to:

$$K E_{ave}(x) = \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((6))$$

One now has a new kind of field which combines energy with force profile. The energy piece is completely Newtonian (or special relativistic). We argue that this is the quantum bound state picture, but the basic idea of force and energy on a similar dual footing already occurs with rest mass which is both inertia (force) and energy mocc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to ask: How should one view quantum physics in terms of force profile in space and energy simultaneously? We argue that already in classical physics, m represents inertia which is force, but at the same energy, mocc. We suggest that this is a useful notion and should be extended to the classical potential $V(x)$. In a Newtonian bound state problem, one writes:

$$p(x) \frac{p(x)^2}{2m} + V(x) = E \quad (\text{one dimension}).$$

This equation gives the impression of only energy, but that is because the force represented by $-d/dx V(x)$ exists at each x with $dx \rightarrow 0$. We suggest that physically $V(x)$ is more than just an energy mapping, it also maps the force distribution in space at the same time. This is an important idea, because if a particle with momentum p and deterministic kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ (consistent with special relativity $v \ll c$), did not provide an impulse hit at its center-of-mass, but in some spatial region about its center-of-mass in a probabilistic manner, then it would not be good enough to write $p^2/2m$ at some x . Rather one needs to create a type of field which demonstrates both energy and force distribution at the same time. We argue that this is exactly what a quantum bound state does. The impulse hit in space probability distribution is $\exp(ipx)$ and so

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) / \left(\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right) \quad ((7))$$

multiplies deterministic energy by a spatial force profile to create a kind of field which represents both energy and force profile. It is this which is matched with $V(x)$. $V(x)$ represents force at each x (in dx), but it is only the average field ((7)) which represents this same physical notion. We argue that this explains why one may write that virtual particles, like photons, exist in an electromagnetic potential. These render force, but a potential is supposed to only represent energy. We argue that it represents both energy and a force distribution at the same time and that this is what the quantum bound state describes. We also argue that deterministic Newtonian mechanics (linked to special relativity), i.e. $p^2/2m$ is present at every energy level and it is not correct to suggest that Newtonian mechanics only emerges in the high energy limit.